

The Condensation of Resorcinol and a few other Aromatic Hydroxy Compounds with some Acids, Esters, Lactones and Lactams.

BY

RAJENDRA NATH SEN

AND

SARBANI SAHAYA GUHA SIRCAR.

A considerable amount of work has been done on the condensation of phenols with the anhydrides of polybasic organic acids, by Baeyer and a host of other investigators.¹

The very wide application of the reaction between phenols and acid anhydrides has established beyond doubt peculiar reactivity of the carbonyl group of the acid anhydride in giving rise to phthalein-like bodies.

A slightly different type of acid anhydride is *o*-sulpho benzoic anhydride, which was also observed by Sohon to react with phenols in the same manner as phthalic anhydride (Amer. Chem. J., 1898, 20, 257). The 'sulpham' of this anhydride (benzoic sulphimide), or 'saccharin,' was also found to behave similarly. (Monnet and Koetschet, Bull. Soc. Chim., 1897, 17 (ii), 690; also Dutt, T. 1922, 121, 2389).

¹ Baeyer (Ber., 1871, 4, 658); Baeyer and Caro (Ber., 1875, 7, 968); Lunge and Burckhardt (Ber., 1884, 17, 1598; Ber 18, 2364. Silberrad, Proc. 1906, 209; Nencki and Sieber (1881, Ai, 671); (1881, A-1, 591 and 811), J. Pr. Chem. [2], 23, 147-156 and 587-550. Succino-rhodamine Ber. 23, B. 811), in more recent years, Quinoloneins (Ghosh, 1919, T. 1104); Citraconeins, Shri Krishna and Pope (1921, T. 289); Camphoreins (Sircar and Dutt, 1922, T. 1283; Shri Krishna, T. 253; and Singh, Rai and Lall T. 1421 in the same year); Phenyl-succoneins, Lapworth and MacRae (1922, T. 2722); Diphenoneins, Dutt (1923, T. 226).

The last mentioned example suggested a study of the reactivity of the carbonyl group in configurations other than that of anhydrides. Besides the case of 'saccharin,' there are a few other instances of such in the literature. Thus, some monobasic organic acids were found by Cohn to react with resorcinol to give rise to what are known as the 'benzeins,' which are very much analogous to phthaleins (Cohn, Ber. 1892, 24, 2064). Another instance of the reactivity of the carbonyl group in giving rise to phthalein-like products, is found in Sri Krishna's work on the condensation of the lactone, coumarin with phenol and resorcin (1921, T. 1420).

The present work has for its object the further study of the reactivity of the carbonyl group specially in configurations not hitherto investigated, in respect of condensation with resorcinol and similar other aromatic hydroxy compounds. It seems that the condensation of this type between acids and phenols has not been studied sufficiently thoroughly so as to establish the generality of the reaction, while the study of the reactivity of esters, lactones and lactams (all of which contain the reactive carbonyl group), presents an almost untrodden ground.

With this object in view, typical acids of the aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic series, have been taken for investigation and found to give phthalein-like products with resorcin, pyrogallol, etc.

The behaviour of esters has also been examined to determine if they were more or less reactive than the acids, and it has been found that, as a rule, the esters react with greater ease than the acids from which they are derived.

As the reactivity of lactones was only indicated by Sri Krishna's work on coumarin (*loc. cit.*), more work on this line seemed desirable to establish the generality of the reaction.

The lactam, isatin has also been examined with the same object, it being found that the lactamic, or the α -carbonyl group may also be made to react with phenol, resorcinol, etc., to give products analogous to phthaleins.

A much more interesting case for study was found in the investigation whether both the carbonyl groups of the anhydrides of dibasic acids can be made to react either simultaneously or successively. This part of the work presents an entirely new aspect of the question, not having been hitherto investigated by previous workers. The present work in this direction goes to show that the reaction does not, under ordinary circumstances, take place with both the carbonyl groups simultaneously, though it is possible to make them react successively, with the same or different phenols, with good yield. Under more drastic conditions, *viz.*, heating longer at higher temperature, with larger quantity of condensing agent, it is also possible to make both the carbonyl groups of phthalic anhydride react simultaneously with resorcinol, though the yield of the desired product is rather small.

The results of the present investigation are briefly as follows:—

In the acid series, two hydroxy acids (salicylic and gallic) have been found to give fluoresceins when heated with resorcin in presence of zinc chloride (powdered and anhydrous), in a current of dry hydrochloric acid to 180-200°C.

Salicylic acid has been found to condense with pyrogallol as well, to give a product non-fluorescent in alkalies or organic solvents.

An amino acid, *viz.*, anthranilic acid, has been condensed with resorcin and diethyl-*m*-amido-phenol and found to give a benzein in the one case, and a rhodamine in the other. The *o*-amino-resorcinol benzein thus obtained, is found to have a fluorescence of the same kind as that of

the *o*-hydroxy compound derived from salicylic acid. Both give orange-green fluorescence in alkaline solutions which however changes to bluish-red on standing,—the change in the case of the amino-benzein taking place with greater ease. The rhodamine gives red solutions with greenfluorescence in acids and organic solvents. The effect of the substitution of amino group for hydroxyl group in the benzeins, is therefore not very marked. The presence of free amino group in the final product is proved by the isocyanide reaction and by the action of nitrous acid.

An aliphatic acid, *viz*, stearic acid, has also been condensed with resorcin, yielding a fluorescein. Unlike the other products this is found to dissolve in benzene and less readily in ether. The compound is found to have only a moderate affinity for animal fibres. The fluorescence is also a little subdued.

Pyromucic acid, a heterocyclic acid, also gives a fluorescein with resorcin. The compound has been obtained by heating mucic acid and resorcin with zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid. In alkaline solution the fluorescence changes from a greenish to a bluish tone on standing.

It is interesting to note that the bromine-content in the bromo derivatives of the above compounds, seems to vary according to the nature of the compound, for some of the compounds give tetra- (those derived from benzoic and salicylic acids), and some di-bromo derivatives (those from gallic and anthranilic acids), when the bromination is effected under similar conditions without taking any precautions. This is in agreement with Cohn's observations regarding similar compounds previously mentioned (*loc. cit.*).

Two esters, those of benzoic and salicylic acids, have also been examined. It is found that the reaction

between them and resorcinol, pyrogallol, etc., takes place with a greater readiness than in the case of corresponding acids. The yields are much better. The greater facility of the reaction in the case of the esters, may be plausibly explained by assuming that the first stage of the reaction consists in the elimination of a mol. of alcohol instead of a mol. of water as in the previous case,

while the subsequent stages are the same in both the cases. The elimination of alcohol may be supposed to take place with greater ease than that of water.

In the study of condensation of lactones, the present work has been chiefly done on coumarin, in extension of previous work. It is found that it also gives a rhodamine (not previously prepared) with diethyl-*m*-amidophenol, which has, properties analogous to true rhodamines, both in colour, dyeing properties, and solubility.

α - and β -naphthols have also been condensed with coumarin, giving rise to phthalein-like bodies. The β -naphthol compound is found to dissolve in caustic soda with strong green fluorescence. The ready solubility in alkali is explained by the non-closure of the lactone ring in the final product. This assumption is confirmed by analytical data which correspond to the structure (IV).

The α -naphthol compound, which was found extremely difficult to purify owing to tar-formation, is also slightly fluorescent in caustic soda solution, due no doubt, to partial α -condensation giving a fluorane-like substance, (V).

The main product being α -naphthol coumarein (VI)

Complete separation could not be effected as both the products dissolve in the same solvents.

Pyrogallol has also been found to condense with coumarin to give a non-fluorescent substance of "gallein-" like nature.

An observation that repeatedly engages the attention in the study of these condensations, is the peculiar behaviour of compounds in which pyrogallol is the second or phenolic component. It is found that all such compounds are non-fluorescent in alkaline solutions as well as in organic solvents, though the only difference between them and the resorcinol derivatives consists in the presence of additional hydroxyl groups in the former, in the *o*-positions to the pyrone-oxygen atom.

Coming at last to the study of the reactivity of both the carbonyl groups in the anhydride of dibasic acids (phthalic anhydride being chosen in the present case), the following observations were made in the course of the present work.

It was found that on heating the anhydride (one mol.) with four mols. of resorcin to 220°C with zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid, no other product than fluorescein was obtained. Phenol-phthalein (a compound in which one of the carbonyl groups has already been acted upon), was next heated with resorcin and zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid to 180-200°C. Curiously enough, it was found that fluorescein was

formed under the circumstances as previously observed by Meyer and Pfothenauer (Ber., 1905, 38, 3958).

Phenol-phthalein was then heated with an excess of resorcinol (about 2.5 mols.) with a larger quantity of zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid to 220°C, for five hours. Under these conditions the desired condensation was effected, and on purification the product was found to be an extremely interesting compound in which both the carbonyl groups of the anhydride were acted upon, the first with phenol, and the second with resorcinol mols. It is thus a compound which contains both a phenol-phthalein and a fluorescein component. The constitution (VII) is given to this compound.

(VII)

(VIII)

It dissolves in alkalis and organic solvents with an intense green fluorescence in no way inferior to that of fluorescein itself. It gives a tetrabromo derivative corresponding to eosin and a di-potassium salt, formulated as in (VIII). The compound is thus doubly quinonoid. The intensity of the colour and fluorescence is no doubt ascribable to 'double symmetric tautomerism,' which it is obviously capable of exhibiting.

The compound may also be regarded as being formed by the condensation of one of the carbonyl groups of phthalic acid with two mols. of phenol, and of the other carbonyl group with two mols. of resorcinol.

To confirm the reactivity of the second carbonyl group of phthaleins, *p*-cresol-phthalein anhydride was prepared according to Drewsen (A. 212, 340-47) by heating phthalic anhydride (one mol.) and *p*-cresol (two mols.) with conc. sulphuric acid. The compound was chosen in preference to *o*-phenol-phthalein anhydride, as the latter is difficult to prepare in any quantity. The anhydride chosen is interesting also in having a pyrone-ring already formed in the molecule. The product of condensation of the anhydride with resorcin, is found to dissolve with less ease in alkalies and to give a solution, the fluorescence of which is less bright than that of fluorescein, being more red and less orange on dilution than fluorescein. The difference is no doubt ascribable to the increased complexity of the mol., and to the presence of methyl groups in *p*-positions to the pyrone-oxygen. It is given the constitution (IX), the potassium salt having the constitution (X).

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

Fluorescein itself when heated with excess of (3 mols.) resorcin, with excess of zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid to 230-40°C for 6 to 7 hours, was found to give a product, which unlike fluorescein, is insoluble in sodium carbonate and precipitated by carbon dioxide from solutions in caustic soda. On purification, this gives a solution in caustic soda, the fluorescence of which is somewhat subdued, and much less bright than that of

fluorescein itself. Analytical results agree with the compound expected.

The last three condensations may be classed with those of the lactones, as the first components in these reactions are compounds of the lactone type. Looked at from this point of view it is hardly surprising that these condensations should be possible, though it must be admitted that they take place under conditions more drastic than in any other case hitherto studied. The heaviness and complexity of the molecules sufficiently explain the difference.

In the lactam series, only one lactam, *viz.*, isatin, has been studied. It was found by Baeyer and Lazarus (Ber. 18, 2637-43), to condense with phenol, toluene, anisole and di-methylaniline in presence of conc. sulphuric acid at ordinary temperatures, the condensation taking place with the β -carbonyl group of isatin.

In connection with the present investigation, phenol and isatin were *heated* with conc. sulphuric acid to 120-30°C for 6 to 7 hours, but the product was identical with "phenol-isatin" obtained by Baeyer to which he gave the constitution (XI).

In the present work, isatin has also been condensed with phenol in the presence of zinc chloride at 180-90°C. The product is found to dissolve in caustic soda with red colour much deeper than that of alkaline solutions of 'phenol-isatin,' and produces no colour effect in alkaline solution by the addition of potassium ferrocyanide while 'phenol-isatin,' under similar conditions gives a violet colour. The difference between the two compounds is ascribed to the condensations having taken place with the α -carbonyl group in one case and with the β -carbonyl group in the other.

Isatin has also been found to condense with resorcin, in the presence of zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid giving a product analogous to fluorescein.

Diethyl-*m*-amidophenol also condenses to give a rhodamine. The resorcin compound gives a di-potassium salt which probably has the constitution (XII)

In this compound, it is interesting to find that though no quinonoid form is possible under ordinary conditions, yet it is fluorescent and coloured. The fluorescence is however slight in alkaline solution, though marked in conc. sulphuric acid solution. By assuming that the lactam-ring is broken by hydrolysis, quinonoid form (XIII) becomes possible. This however does not explain the existence of the di-potassium salt.

The following further experiments have been made to establish whether the α - or the β - carbonyl group of isatin reacted in these compounds.

(1) Both isatin, and 'phenol-isatin,' as well as the present products liberate nitrogen with nitrous acid.

(2) With chloroform and alcoholic potash isatin and also 'phenol-isatin' are unaffected. The present products react vigorously with the reagents, and the smell of isocyanide slowly develops in the mixture on standing. This may be due to the breach in the lactam ring by hydrolysis, and formation of a free amido group.

(3) Both 'phenol-isatin' and the present products are insoluble in sodium carbonate and precipitated by carbon-dioxide from solution in caustic soda probably because under ordinary conditions the lactam ring is unaffected.

The difference in behaviour in isocyanide-reaction may be ascribed to the fact that while in 'phenol-isatin' the

β -carbonyl group of isatin was reactive, in the present products, the α -(or the true lactamic) carbonyl group reacts with phenol, resorcin, diethyl-*m*-amidophenol and also pyrogallol, rendering the lactamic ring unstable, and readily opened by alcoholic caustic potash setting free the amido group. In fact, the present compounds may be looked upon as being derived from isatinic acid in the same manner as the amino-benzein (already described), is derived from anthranilic acid,—the two acids being comparable.

Pyrogallol has also been found to condense readily with isatin yielding a product, similar to other pyrogallol derivatives, which gives deeply coloured non-fluorescent solutions in alkalis and organic solvents.

p-Cresol has also been condensed with isatin, giving a product insoluble in acids and alkalis, but dissolving readily in glacial acetic acid and conc. sulphuric acid in the latter solvent with slight fluorescence. Its properties are therefore analogous to those of *p*-cresolphthaloin anhydride.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General observations.

The following observations may be made regarding the general procedure followed in the preparation of the compounds described in this paper.

One mol. of the acid, ester, lactone, or lactam was heated with two mols. of resorcin, pyrogallol, etc., with powdered anhydrous zinc chloride to 180-200°C, for three to four hours, generally in a current of dry hydrochloric acid. The cases in which this method was departed from is noted under the individual preparations. No

hydrochloric acid gas was used in the preparation of the rhodamines.

The purification of the compounds was effected by powdering the crude product wherever possible, extracting with boiling solution of dilute hydrochloric acid to remove zinc chloride, dissolving the washed residue in dil. caustic soda solution, and precipitating with dil. acetic acid or hydrochloric acid. This operation was repeated two or three times when necessary, and the washed and dried residue crystallized from alcohol, acetone or pyridine as the case might be. In some cases hydrochloric acid precipitated the product in a resinous form from alkaline solutions, in which cases dil. acetic acid was employed instead. In cases where the product was not sufficiently purified by precipitation, it was boiled with animal charcoal in alcoholic solution, and the filtered solution poured into water and then the washed residue crystallized from alcohol, etc.

In some cases, the removal of zinc chloride proved to be a matter of considerable difficulty, and the purification was effected by repeated extraction with hot dil. hydrochloric acid solution, both in the first stage, and in the subsequent stages. In these cases the final purification was effected from acetone.

Bromination was effected by adding slight excess of bromine to an alcoholic solution of the product, and allowing to stand overnight. The ppt. was filtered, washed with hot water, dissolved in caustic soda, precipitated with hydrochloric acid and finally crystallized from alcohol. As mentioned previously, in some cases di-, and in others tetra-bromo derivatives were thus obtained.

The potassium salts were prepared by suspending the finely powdered substance in hot water, adding a slightly less than the theoretical quantity of caustic potash (purified by extraction with absolute alcohol) and

constantly stirring the mixture heated on the water-bath, till solution was complete. It was filtered from the excess of the substance and the filtrate evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. It was then powdered, washed with absolute alcohol, and then extracted with the minimum quantity of water, and the aqueous solution concentrated, when the potassium salt separated.

Only two benzoyl derivatives, those of the salicylic acid and the phenol-phthalein compounds, were prepared by the usual method. As these derivatives contain nearly the same percentage of carbon and hydrogen as the parent substances, and as particularly it was practically impossible in many cases, to distinguish between the mono- or poly-benzoylated products by combustion results, this class of derivatives were not prepared in the case of other compounds.

The rhodamines were generally formed at somewhat lower temps. and less heating was required for their formation. For purification, they were powdered, extracted repeatedly with hot water and hot dil. caustic soda to remove zinc chloride and dissolved in hot dil. hydrochloric acid and precipitated with caustic soda or ammonium hydroxide. This was repeated and the dried product purified from alcohol, acetone or pyridine. In cases of difficulty of purification, the alcoholic solution was boiled with animal charcoal, and the filtered solution was poured into water till a turbidity was produced. The solution was then filtered and allowed to stand overnight with more water. The ppt. which separated was then purified by crystallisation from alcohol, etc.

THE CONDENSATIONS WITH ACIDS. (A)

1. *Resorcinol-gallein*.—3.5 gms. of gallic acid and 4.5 gms. of resorcin were heated on the oil-bath till the mixture melted (at about 200°C). At this stage, the flame

was removed, and 3 gms. of zinc chloride were added in small quantities at a time. A vigorous reaction ensued, and the mixture completely melted. The temp. was lowered to 190°C and kept there till the vigour of the reaction subsided. Afterwards the temp. was raised to 200°C and kept there for 3 hours. All this time, a slow current of hydrochloric acid gas was passed over the mixture.

The purification was effected by the general method. Yield 80% of the theoretical. It is a dark-red powder dissolving in alkalis and organic solvents with deep green-red fluorescence. Soluble in alcohol, more so in acetone, insoluble in acetic acid, ether and benzene. Dyes wool and silk brownish shades deepening on chroming. It does not melt up to 250°C. It gives a red di-bromo derivative.

Found: C=67·7, 67·72% ; H=3·96, 4·02% . $C_{19}H_{13}O_6$ requires C=67·85% , H=3·6% .

Di-bromo derivative—is a red powder, giving red solution in alkali without fluorescence. Dyes wool and silk deep red. It does not melt up to 250°C.

Found: Br=31·97% . $C_{19}H_{11}O_6Br_2$ requires Br=32·4% .

2. *Resorcinol-o-amino-benzoin*.—4 gms. of anthranilic acid and 6·8 gms. of resorcin were mixed with 5 gms. of zinc chloride and heated for 4 hours to 180°C in a current of dry hydrochloric acid. Purification was effected as in the case of 'resorcinol salicylein.' (Sen and Sinha, Amer. Chem. J., 1923, 12, 298±.) It was finally crystallized from alcohol and dried in the vacuum desiccator. Yield about 70% of the theoretical. The substance closely resembles resorcinol salicylein in colour, fluorescence, solubilities and dyeing properties. It softens at 175-77°C. It gives a di-bromo, and a mono-potassium derivative.

Found: N=4·36% , 4·41% . $C_{19}H_{13}O_5N$ requires N=4·6% .

Di-bromo derivative.—Closely resembles the bromo-derivative of resorcinol salicylein in properties. Dyes red shades. Decomposes at 195°C. Found: Br = 34.4%. $C_{19}H_{17}O_3NBr_2$ requires Br = 34.7%.

Mono-potassium derivative.—Dissolves in water with green-red fluorescence changing to bluish-red on standing. Found: K = 11.6%. $C_{19}H_{15}O_3NK$ requires K = 11.4%.

3. *Resorcinol-stearic acid*.—3 gms. of stearic acid (1 mol.), were mixed with 3.5 gms. (3 mols.), of resorcin and heated with the addition of 3 gms. of zinc chloride to 200-210°C for 4½ hours. A large excess of resorcin was employed to prevent the presence of unaltered stearic acid in the final product. To ensure the completion of the reaction the heating was effected for a longer time than usual at a higher temp.

The product was purified by the general method, and finally from benzene. It was dried in the vacuum desiccator. Unlike the other products it was soluble in benzene and to a less extent in ether. The fluorescence was slight but appreciable, and the colour deep red. On standing a bluish tone is assumed. The product has very slight affinity for wool and silk. It softens at 152°C.

Found: C = 79.78, 79.70%. H = 9.5, 9.48%. $C_{30}H_{44}O_3$ requires C = 80%, H = 9.33%.

4. *Resorcinol-pyromucic acid*.—4 gms. of mucic acid and 4 gms. of resorcinol were gradually heated with 4 gms. of zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid. At 140°C a vigorous reaction ensued. When it subsided a little, the temp. was gradually raised to 200°C and kept there for 3½ hours. Purification was effected by the general method. Finally from pyridine. The product is similar to the stearic acid compound in colour and fluorescence, but has more pronounced dyeing properties. It is however insoluble in benzene or ether, and not very soluble in alcohol.

The fluorescence is also slight. It does not melt up to 250°C.

Found: C=73.0%, H=3.9%. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C=73.37%, H=3.6%.

5. *Pyrogallol-salicylein*.—3 gms. of salicylic acid and 5 gms. of pyrogallol were heated with 3.5 gms. of zinc chloride for 4 hours to 180-90°C. Purification was effected by the general method. Finally from a mixture of pyridine and water (2:1). The alkaline solution has a deep red-brown colour, without fluorescence, as also solutions in organic solvents. It is not very soluble in alcohol, but dissolves in acetone, and a mixture of pyridine and water. It does not melt up to 250°C.

Found: C=67.6%, H=3.82%. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C=67.85%, H=3.57%.

6. *Anthranilo-rhodamine*.—3 gms. (slight excess of 1 mol.) of anthranilic acid and 6.5 gms. of di-ethyl-*m*-amido phenol were finely ground together and heated on the oil-bath till the mixture melted. Powdered zinc chloride was added in small quantities with constant stirring. The mixture was then gradually heated to 180°C for 3 hours, till the melt solidified. The cold mass was finely powdered, extracted repeatedly with hot water and hot dil. caustic soda to remove zinc chloride. It was then dissolved in warm dil. hydrochloric acid and precipitated with ammonium hydroxide or caustic soda. This was repeated and the washed residue finally purified from alcohol and obtained in the form of a pink powder. It dissolves readily in acids with green-red fluorescence, more marked in organic solvents. Yield about 60% of the theoretical. It softens at about 230°C. Dyes wool and silk an impure violet shade (with a mixture of green).

Found: N=9.56, 9.62%. $C_{27}H_{23}O_2N_3$ requires N=9.74%.

CONDENSATIONS WITH ESTERS. (B)

7. *Resorcinol-salicylein*.—A mixture of 8 gms. of methyl salicylate and 4.5 gms. of resorcin was heated with zinc chloride with an air-condenser in a current of dry hydrochloric acid. The temp. was raised gradually to 200°C and kept there for 4 hours. The purification was effected by the method for the identical product obtained from the acid. Finally purified from acetone. Yield 85% of the theoretical. Does not melt up to 260°C.

Found: C=74.84%, 74.86%; H=4.38, 4.3%. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C=75.0%, H=4.0%.

8. *Pyrogallol-salicylein*.—3 gms. of oil of wintergreen and 5 gms. of pyrogallol were heated with 4 gms. of zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid for 4 hours with an air-condenser. The product was identical with that obtained from the acid. Yield about 85% of the theoretical.

Found: C=67.64%, H=3.72%. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C=67.85%, H=3.57%.

CONDENSATIONS WITH LACTONES. (C)

9. *β -Naphthol-coumarein*.—A mixture of 3 gms. of coumarin and 6 gms. of β -naphthol was heated for 4 hours at 180-90°C in a current of dry hydrochloric acid, together with 4 gms. of zinc chloride. The product was extracted repeatedly with boiling dil. hydrochloric acid solution to remove zinc chloride, washed with hot water, extracted with caustic soda and the solution pptd. with dil. acetic acid solution (hydrochloric acid threw down the substance in a pasty form). The operation was repeated twice. After each precipitation the ppt. was boiled with dil. hydrochloric acid to remove traces of zinc chloride the removal of which was found difficult to accomplish. Purified first from boiling alcohol containing animal charcoal, and then from acetone. (A portion of the

crude product was left after first extraction with caustic soda solution, but was not further investigated.) It was dried in the vacuum desiccator. It is a yellowish brown powder not very soluble in alcohol, but dissolves in acetone, glacial acetic acid and conc. sulphuric acid with green fluorescence. It is pptd. by carbon dioxide from alkaline solution. It softens at 115°C. It has very feeble affinity for animal fibres.

Found: C=83.56, 83.4%; H=5.2, 4.8%. $C_{20}H_{10}O_3$, H_2O , or $C_{20}H_{20}O_3$ requires C=83.65%, H=4.8%.

10. *α -Naphthol-coumarin*.—3 gms. of coumarin and 6 gms. of α -naphthol were heated with 4 gms. of zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid for 3 hours to 180°C. There was a great deal of tar formation, which reduced the yield to 40% of the theoretical. After preliminary precipitations as in the case of the β -naphthol compound, the product was dissolved in alcohol, and boiled with animal charcoal for 10 minutes. The cooled filtrate was poured into water till a turbidity was produced. It was filtered and the filtrate allowed to stand overnight with more water. The ppt. thus obtained was finally purified from acetone and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It is a dark brown powder dissolving in caustic soda with red colour. It softens at about 117°C. It has no appreciable affinity for animal fibres.

Found: C=80.38, 80.02%; H=4.89, 4.9%. $C_{22}H_{22}O_4$ requires C=80.18%, H=5.07%.

13. *Pyrogallol-coumarin*.—3 gms. of coumarin were heated with 5 gms. of pyrogallol and 3 gms. of zinc chloride to 180-90°C for 4 hours in a current of dry hydrochloric acid. The product was analogous in properties to other pyrogallol derivatives and purified by analogous method. Finally from alcohol. It does not melt up to 250°C.

Found : C=66.2%, H=4.16%. $C_{21}H_{13}O_6 \cdot H_2O$ requires C=66.49%, H=3.96%.

14. *Coumarin-rhodamine*.—3 gms. of coumarin and 7 gms. of diethyl-*m*-amido phenol were heated with 3 gms. of zinc chloride to 180-90°C for 3 hours, till the melt completely solidified. The purification was effected as in the case of 'anthranilo-rhodamine.' Only the alcoholic solution was boiled with animal charcoal and to the cool filtrate, water was added till a turbidity was produced. It was filtered, and the filtrate allowed to stand with more water. The ppt. thrown down was filtered, and finally purified from acetone. It dissolves in acids with a violet colour, and greenish fluorescence, more marked in organic solvents. Softens at 156°C. Dyes wool and silk violet shades.

Found: N=6.16, 6.2%. $C_{22}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires N=6.36%.

15. *Phenol-resorcinol-phthalein*.—6.5 gms. (1 mol.) of phenol-phthalein, and 5.5 gms. ($2\frac{1}{2}$ mols.) of resorcin, were heated with 5 gms. of zinc chloride to 210-15°C for $4\frac{1}{2}$ hours. Purified by the general method. Finally from alcohol. Yield 70% of the theoretical. It is an orange powder somewhat soluble in hot water, more so in acetone, alcohol. The alkaline solution shows a fluorescence of the same nature and degree as fluorescein. It does not melt up to 250°C. It gives a tetra-bromo, and a di-potassium, and a di-benzoyl derivative. Dyes a greenish yellow shade.

Found: C=76.23, 76.30%, H=4.38, 4.52%, $C_{32}H_{22}O_6$ requires C=76.47%, H=4.4%.

Tetra-bromo derivative.—Orange powder dissolving in alkalis with some fluorescence. Dyes wool and silk red shades. It does not melt up to 250°C. Found: Br=39.3%. $C_{32}H_{18}O_6Br_4$ requires Br=39.1%.

Di-potassium derivative.—Found: K=13.9%. $C_{32}H_{18}O_6K_2$ requires K=13.8%.

Di-benzoyl derivative.—Melts at 156-58°C. Found: C=77.5%, H=4.4%. $C_{26}H_{30}O_2$ requires C=77.74%, H=4.22%.

15A. *Fluorescein*.—3.2 gms. of phenol-phthalein were heated with 2.5 gms. of resorcin, with 2.5 gms. of zinc chloride for 3 to 4 hours to 180-200°C. The purification was effected by the general method. Finally crystallized from alcohol. It has all the properties of fluorescein.

Found: C=72.36%, H=4.0%. Fluorescein, $C_{20}H_{12}O_4$ requires C=72.3%, H=3.7%.

16. *Resorcinol-p-cresolphthalein*.—3.3 gms. of *p*-cresolphthalein anhydride and 2.5 gms. of resorcin were heated together with zinc chloride to 200-220°C for 4½ hours in a current of dry hydrochloric acid. It was purified by the general method, finally from acetone. It is a red powder, soluble in caustic soda with green-red fluorescence less bright than that of fluorescein. It is precipitated by carbon dioxide from this solution. Soluble in acetone and pyridine, less soluble in alcohol. Softens at about 220°C. Gives a di-potassium derivative.

Found: C=79.36, 79.42%; H=5.0, 4.92%. $C_{34}H_{24}O_4$ requires C=79.68%, H=4.67%.

Di-potassium derivative.—Found: K=12.9%. $C_{34}H_{22}O_4K_2$ requires K=13.2%.

17. *Resorcinol-fluorescein*.—3.5 gms. (1 mol.) of fluorescein, and 3.5 gms. (3 mols.) of resorcin, were heated together with 4 gms. of zinc chloride for 5 hours to 230-40°C. The purification was effected, after removal of zinc chloride by extracting the product with sodium carbonate solution to remove unchanged fluorescein. It was then washed, dissolved in caustic soda and pptd. with carbon dioxide. It was re-dissolved in caustic soda pptd. by hydrochloric acid, dried, and purified finally from a mixture of pyridine and water (2:1). The product unlike

fluorescein is insoluble in sodium carbonate. Alkaline solutions have a fluorescence less bright than that of fluorescein. It decomposes at about 230°C.

Found: C=73.86, 73.98%; H=3.84, 3.86%. $C_{22}H_{20}O_7$, requires C=74.4%, H=3.87%. Fluorescein requires C=72.2%, H=3.7%.

CONDENSATIONS WITH LACTAMS. (D)

18. *Besorcinol-isatinein*.—3 gms. of isatin and 4.5 gms. of resorcin were heated for 3 hours with zinc chloride to 180-90°C, in current of dry hydrochloric acid. The purification was effected by the general method. Finally from alcohol. Yield about 75% of the theoretical. It is an orange powder, dissolving in alkalis with slight fluorescence, more marked in conc. sulphuric acid solution. Does not melt up to 265°C. It dyes wool and silk orange shades from an acid bath. It gives a di-potassium and a tetrabromo derivative.

Found: N=3.84, 3.98%. $C_{20}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N=4.2%.

Di-potassium derivative.—Found: K=19.5%. $C_{20}H_{11}O_4K_2N$ requires K=19.2%.

Tetra-bromo derivative.—Dyes red shades. Decomposes at 230°C. Found: Br=49.7%. $C_{20}H_5O_4NBr_4$ requires Br=49.4%.

19. *Isatin-rhodamine*.—3 gms. of isatin and 6.5 gms. of diethyl-*m*-amido phenol were heated with 4.5 gms. of zinc chloride for 3 hours to 180°C. The purification was effected as in the case of the anthranilic acid compound. Finally from acetone. Dissolves in acids with a green-red fluorescence. It softens at 242°C. It dyes wool and silk an impure violet shade.

Found: N=9.3, 9.2%. $C_{22}H_{21}O_2N_2$ requires N=9.5%.

20. *Pyrogallol-isatinein*.—3.5 gms. of isatin and 6 gms. of pyrogallol were heated with 4 gms. of zinc chloride

for 3 hours to 180°C. Purification was effected by the general method. Finally from acetone. It has properties similar to other pyrogallol derivatives, giving non-fluorescent deeply coloured solutions in alkalis and organic solvents. Does not melt up to 250°C.

Found: N=3.7, 3.74%. $C_{20}H_{18}O_6N$ requires N=3.86%.

21. *Phenol-isatinein*.—3.5 gms. of isatin and 3 gms. of phenol were heated with 4 gms. of zinc chloride for 4 hours to 190°C. The product was steam-distilled and the residue purified by the usual method. Finally from alcohol. The product is a greyish powder dissolving in alkalis with a red colour. It softens at about 285°C.

Found: N=4.2, 4.24%. $C_{20}H_{18}O_5N$ requires N=4.41%.

22. *p-Cresol-isatinein anhydride*.—3.5 gms. of isatin and 5.5 gms. of *p*-cresol were heated together with 4 gms. of zinc chloride in a current of dry hydrochloric acid for 2½ hours at 180°C. The product after removal of zinc chloride was extracted with glacial acetic acid and the solution poured into water. The ppt. was filtered, washed and crystallized from glacial acetic acid. Obtained as a greyish powder. Dissolves readily in acetic acid and in conc. sulphuric acid with faint fluorescence. Does not melt up to 250°C.

Found: N=4.0%. $C_{22}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N=4.28%.

PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,

CALCUTTA,

[Received, August 21, 1924.]
